

Introduction of process in embedded programming supporting students' self-efficacy - case study

O. Schultz

DTU Engineering Technology,
Ballerup, Denmark
ORCID 0000-0003-1813-6355

T. Blaszczyk

DTU Engineering Technology,
Ballerup, Denmark
ORCID 0000-0002-1742-6441

Conference Key Areas: *Student Engagement, Teaching methods, Assessments*

Keywords: *metacognitive process, self-efficacy, problem solving, self-awareness, self-management, vignette questions*

ABSTRACT

This work is directed towards the improvement of programming skills for students on the 2nd semester of Electrical Engineering (EE) BEng signed up for the “Digital Electronics and Programming” (DEP) course. The goal is to support students who tend to drop out in the first half of the semester or give up and not show up at oral exams. In our research hypothesis we state: Decreasing and eliminating negative emotional experiences will increase student’s self-efficacy thereby lowering dropout. We experiment with a programming process guide in text and video to gain students' capability in solving programming problems and increase metacognitive awareness. Additionally, we measure students' emotional experience of programming by using a special self-assessment vignette inquiry. For comparison purposes we introduced the same measurement methodology in 2021 on the courses where there is no focus on the process guideline. The results show a positive effect on lowering the negative emotional impact when students use a programming process guide. The article describes the theoretical background based on literature studies for both the process and the students' self-assessment, and discusses results achieved in relation to the findings in the literature. The preliminary results are described in [8] and in paper here we present recent outcomes for the autumn 2021 and spring 2022 semester over 9 weeks.

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. Observation and theoretical foundation

Several papers [1][2][3], show that strong students' self-efficacy has an influence on their ability to learn programming and tackle many kinds of problems which arise (compiler message, logical faults, etc.). Students with a lower self-efficacy have a higher negative self-assessment. During the last 7 years when the DEP course has been offered, we have observed that 10 - 20% of the students give up or do not

show up at the exam. The literature describes several criteria by which students evaluate their programming abilities. For example, prior experiences, speed of solving assignments, grades, social comparisons, and whether their program works, expectations in fluency [2] [3]. Furthermore, students' performance compared to other students, where students construct their perceptions of ability compared with other students, for example in group/teamwork. These factors may have an impact on how strong the negative or positive self-assessment is and thereby influence students' self-efficacy. Self-efficacy is part of the Bandura's [4] social cognitive theory and described as: "to believe in one's capabilities to organise and execute courses in action required to produce given attainments". Gorson, J et.al.[1] studied why students think they are bad at programming by using self-assessment by using 13 moments of programming. The study was carried out in computer science courses for novice programmers at 3 universities. They concluded: "We also found that the frequency with which students negatively self-assessment correlates with their overall self-efficacy in their programming courses." Studies about self-assessment and self-awareness in computer science courses inspired us to do the project within Scholarship of Teaching and Learning (SoTL). In SoTL work we try to find answer to the research question: "Can metacognitive processes help students to gain more self-confidence and thus continue to be active during the course?" and one of the hypotheses leads to the statement: "Lowering negative emotional experiences increase self-efficacy." For helping students in programming assignments, problem solving and for seeing if it could lower the students drop-out during the semester we introduce a process in programming hands-on assignments to show and guide how to solve programming problems inspired by Loksa [7]. The process is based upon literature study [5],[6] discussing learning processes when dealing with programming problems, self-efficacy, and self-confidence when programming. Next, we measure students' self-emotional experiences using a self-assessment tool inspired by Gorson 's et.al [1] work for measuring the emotional impact when programming. We customized this framework for measuring quantitatively of what degree students emotional impact changes due to receiving help from our guideline to be more self-confident and get less negative influence. At the same time be motivated to follow the course and go to the exam. The self-assessment is done by using 13 moments of programming which a professional would come through. Therefore, it is relevant to use at our bachelor (Diploma-engineering 3½ year program) studies in Electrical Engineering and IT (Information Technology) and Electronic Engineering studies. Gorson et. al [4] also posed 4 general questions in a survey for qualitatively testing self-efficacy. Due to limited time and constraints, we do not focus on this in our studies. Neither we do not measure self-efficacy in programming as Steinhof et al. [5] In contradiction to Gorson, we use the vignette questionnaire survey 3 times during the semester for testing if the introduction of a process in programming helps students to have fewer negative feelings when dealing with programming and thereby, we assume that the less negative impact has a positive impact on the self-efficacy. It is not in the scope to measure the self-efficacy by tools as suggested and used in [5]. We did start the experiment in the autumn 2021. In O. Schultz et. al [8] we show results by using process guidelines instead of using the Moments of Programming Vignette survey.

Conclusion was that using the process guideline lowers the negative self-assessment.

1.2 Programming processes

Learning how to program involves more than just syntax, control, and data structures. It also involves mental scaffolding around the learner where the learner can place knowledge and become metacognitive aware [7]. That means the student understands where one is in the problem-solving process. Several studies describe and discuss problem solving stages when dealing with programming. Loksa. D et al and Prather et. al [6][7] investigated metacognitive awareness for novice programmers and they identified 6 specific stages in learning to solve programming problems. The stages are: (1) reinterpret the prompt, (2) search for analogous problems, (3) search for a solution, (4) evaluate a potential solution, (5) implement a solution, (6) evaluate the implemented solution. That study and other studies [3][6] lead to our process being introduced for 2nd semester students in the first week and used repeatedly when solving the assignments. The programming guideline process introduced to students on 2nd semester EE from first class-lecture is adjusted according to the DEP course content and hands-on exercises to be carried out by students. The process used is presented below:

1. Read the whole assignment. Does the assignment make sense?
2. What could a solution to the task /subtasks look like? Outline the solution with pseudocode and / or a flow-chart.
3. Imagine a simulated execution of your hypothetical program / parts of the program. Use your pseudocode and flowchart. Simulate running the hypothesis program. Does the expected happen?
4. What can the C-code for the sub-task / task solution look like?
5. Open Microchip studio, start a new project, select GCC C executable, give the project a suitable name and place the project somewhere where you can find it again. Press ok. Choose to use an ATmega2560. Program the solution you have found for each sub-task found under 2.
6. Does the program perform the hypothetical run-through performed in 3?

The subsequent process steps help students to focus on problem refinement and narrow to the solution which unloads unnecessary confusion and thoughts about overall assignment.

1.3 Didactics used in the Digital Electronics and Programming (DEP) course

The experiments are done in DEP course. The content consists of a digital electronics programme supported with practical programming tasks with focus on microcontroller interfacing peripheral devices. Observations and surveys from students are collected and shown in section 3. The students must understand how

to read a complex datasheet and use the information to set up microcontroller-registers by C-programming language for the distinct kinds of interfaces. Compared to standard C-programming courses it requires also comprehensive understanding of electronic device manufacturer documentation and the way of essential information transformation from datasheet to a program. The teaching method used in this course is blended learning. Before each lecture, the students are asked to watch a video about the topic for the coming class and take a quiz about the content in the video and the related chapter in the course-book. Students work on 5 different assignments for 13 weeks, and 4 of the assignments are for hand-in in pair groups. For each assignment they hand-in a report documenting various aspects of the programming work. The requirements for taking the exam are all submitted reports approved as well as the answered quizzes taken during classes. The exam is oral where students randomly choose one question out of six from the digital electronic field and they present orally the answers to the question. Furthermore, the examiner asks questions related to C-programming part in the last assignment

2. Data collection

2.1 Characteristics of the classes in subsequent years from 2017 to 2021

Gradings of the classes since 2017 up to 2022 have been analysed for finding the exact numbers of students dropping out at the examination. The data is listed in the Table 1 and described below

year	stud. spring	not met	median	average	std. Div.	stud. autumn.	not met	median	average	std. div.
2017	64	6	7	7.25	3.96	29	6	7	6.86	3.95
2018	64	7	7	7.50	3.46	25	3	10	7.86	3.82
2019	49	15	10	8.23	2.92	33	14	10	8.78	3.55
2020	52	10	7	7.40	3.00	25	4	7	7.80	3.29
2021	59	10	7	7.38	3.64	34	9	10	8.84	2.93

Table 1. Students' enrolment statistics in particular year.

The course is taught twice a year, Spring and Autumn. The column "stud. spring" and "stud. autumn" shows the number of students enrolled to the exam. Next is shown number of students who do not show up. The grading scale is pass: 02, 4,7,10,12 (excellent) and not pass: -03 and 00. The median grade-values are shown together with the average grade and the standard deviation. Table 1. shows the grades are higher in the smaller classes but the standard deviation is greater. The number of students who do not show up is little greater in the autumn. The students in the autumn semester are more diverse in background as some have been working fulltime before studying. That could explain the larger drop out. Overall, if the process introduction can bring some of these students to the exam, then it could mean less students drop the exam, due to stronger self-confidence. Process introduction in autumn does not show any changes as 26% did not enrol to the exam. Even in 2020 15% did not enrol to the exam.

2.2 Measuring emotional impact

Purpose in this work is to measure if the process guideline helps students lowering the negative self-assessment and thereby continuing the course and participate in the examination.

The 13 moments of programming with the vignettes in [1] is translated into Danish. We have made a pre-test on students before using the 13 moments of programming vignettes. Based upon that we adjusted the vignette belonging to each moment of programming, we substituted the names with 1st and 2nd person singular subject pronouns. Due to the time, we had for the experiment we use Google form to collect results and thereby the scale from 1 to 6. Where 1 means less negative impact and 6 is most negative impact. In the Gorson study they used a scale of strongly agree for the most negative impact and most positive impact as total disagree. We do not directly use the positive impact. We assume less negative (1) is reflected as positive and gains more self-efficacy. The survey is carried out in the 1st lesson and 7th in autumn and 8th lesson in spring and the 3rd one is done in the last week 13th (last lecture). The full text for the 13 moments of programming with vignette statements is presented in [9].

3. Results

3.1 Answers to the self-assessments

The population in the autumn was 27 students in the 1st survey and second survey 22 students. In the spring 46 students participated in the 1st survey and the 2nd survey 33 students answered. The 1st survey is done during the lesson 10 minutes after start. The survey is performed without influence from the teachers. The 2nd survey was carried out in the middle of the semester during the lesson after the first break. The participants are also asked about their programming experiences and what programming language they know. They have an opportunity as well to comment upon the vignette survey. These extra answers show the appr. 50% are novices and 50% had been programming before enrolling on the education from 1 to 8 years more and less. The moments of programming shown below are indicated by letters from A to M:

- A. A Simple Error.
- B. Start over.
- C. Do not understand the error message.
- D. Stop programming to plan.
- E. Get help from others.
- F. Spending time looking up syntax.
- G. Spending time planning in the beginning.
- H. Spends a lot of time solving a problem.
- I. Do not know how to get started.
- J. Spends a long time finding a simple mistake.
- K. Struggling to find the error.
- L. Unable to complete within expected time.
- M. Do not understand the problem of the task.

In most of the moments except B, I and M, the self-assessment is measured on the general programming work, where the compiler and IDE is used. And the process

guideline does not address that. Whereas during the semester students should be more used to the IDE and the compiler, therefore lowering the negative-self-assessment. For each moment from A to M there is a vignette. An example of vignette related to M is: “You solve your programming task. You do not understand what the task asks you to do. You feel sad and frustrated because you cannot even understand the question. How much does it affect you?”. The vignette for each moment of programming can be seen in [9]. In this paper we present the self-assessment data of moments of programming shown in table 2 where we found the greatest changes and scores in the autumn 2021 and compared with the data from spring 2022. In Table 2 data is compared for self-assessment on five moments of programming, and the data is compared to data in Goron’s [1] study ([10] show results for all 13 moments of programming). Data shown in Table 2 is created by choosing to use scores of 4 and up to 6 interpreted as negative which may have the most impact on the self-efficacy. We present only moments with highest scores. In general, the Table 2 data have the same orders of magnitude as Gorson’s study [1]. The moment: C.” Do not understand the error message” are also having a negative emotional effect together with moment I. “Do not know how to get started,” moment L. “Not being able to finish in time” and moment M. “Do not understand the problem of the task.” The moment C has decreased by 10% lower for the spring class which may be because students get used to the IDE and the compiler messages. But it is not happening in the Autumn semester. For the moment L “Unable to finish in time.” the score is lowered in Autumn but increased in spring semester, which may be in a relation to workload from the other courses. The process introduced should lower the negative self-assessment for moment I where the figures show for the autumn class, but not for the Spring class. Also, for moment M self-assessment score should be lowered due to the process introduction as seen decreased by 6% for Spring and 36% for the Autumn The moment K Struggling finding the error assessed less negative score as expected during the semester, as students get used to the compiler messages

Moments of programming	Week 1 F21	Week 7 F21	Week 1 S22	Week 8 s22	Gorson [1]
C. Do not understand error message:	44%	55%	72%	61%	62%
I. Do not know how to get started:	70%	59%	67%	66%	84%
K. Struggling to find the error:	56%	14%	35%	30%	59%
L. Unable to complete within expected time:	48%	32%	46%	57%	50%
M. Do not understand the problem of the task:	77%	41%	72%	66%	79%

Table 2. Negative self-assessment in % of total participant.

The data has also been analysed regarding the students’ background in programming before the study start. The results are shown in Table 3 and 4. The data is split into students who have no programming experiences before the study start and students who have experience in programming before study start. Data

shows here that the novices have a higher median value, and the 75% quartile is higher compared to students who had been doing programming before the study. It shows over time when you get more experienced you also act more professionally, and the negative self-assessment is lower. Regarding moments I to M the novices also self-assess more negatively than the experienced students. And novice students in spring does self-assess more negatively for moments I and M, compared to Autumn semester students. Moment M “Do not understand the problem of the task may also address capability of student’s understanding of the assignment text. That shows teachers need to be very aware of formulation of assignment

Experiences - not novice				no experiences - novice		
vignette	25%	50%	75%	25%	50%	75%
C	2.00	3.0	5.00	4	5	5
I	2.75	4.5	6.00	5	6	6
L	1.00	3.0	5.00	3	4	6
M	2.00	4.0	5.00	4	5	5

Table 3. Quartiles for the Spring semester class data split in novice and not novice.

Experiences - not novice				no experiences - novice		
vignette	25%	50%	75%	25%	50%	75%
C	1.0	2	3.0	2.0	3	4.0
I	2.0	4	4.5	2.5	4	5.0
L	2.0	2	3.5	2.0	3	4.0
M	2.0	3	4.5	2.5	4	5.5

Table 4. Quartiles for the Autumn semester class split in novice and not novice.

3.2 Survey about the process

In the 10th week of the semester, we asked students about the uses of the process. We asked these questions in a written survey: **a.** How much does the process help

you understand what the program / sub-program should perform, **b.** How much confidence the process gives when you need to program, **c.** Was it clear from the start of the course what the process was to be used for? On a scale from 0 to 6. And in spring 2022 we added two questions more **d.** Does the process guide increase your problem-solving skills in programming? **e.:** will you faster solve programming problem without process guide?" The Table 5 shows that 47% to 55% of students find the process useful when using scores 4 up to 6.

Year	N. stud.	a \geq 4	b \geq 4	c \geq 4	d \geq 4	e \geq 4
Autumn 21	19	9 (47%)	10 (52%)	12 (63%)		
Spring 22	31	17 (55%)	11 (35%)	8 (26%)	18 (58%)	3 (10%)

Table 5. Evaluation of the process Spring 2022 and autumn 2021.

The question b. about confidence shows a different picture. The class in autumn finds it raises the confidence, but only 35% in the Spring 22. The answers to the question c if it was clear what the process should be used for, indicates that even the process actively was used from 2nd week in the Spring semester only 26% understand it. Better in the Autumn by 63%. Therefore, we need in the future to explain better why it is important for students to use process and how to work with it. The question d. is only asked in the spring for getting more understanding about how much support the process gives students. 58% of the students find it helpful in problem solving. Only 10% find it as a waste of time by answering question e.

4. Conclusions

We find the changes in scores analysed in the autumn indicate lowering scores for the moments of programming during the semester, by introducing the process guide in the course (DEP) and students' self-assessment using the 13 moments of programming with vignettes [9], We can conclude the process could have an impact on students lowering negative self-assessment for the moment M and I as the self-assessment is lower at the end of the semester. But the formulation of assignment text may also have an impact. It can be concluded students with experiences before the study have less negative score in self-assessment. Which confirms that the moments of programming are defined from the way a professional works and therefore students with a previous background are more used to tackling the moments of programming. From the Table 5 we see that students find the process useful approximately 50% and 35% to 52% of students find the process gives more confidence. From Table 1 the students not participating in the exam do not show any changes in the Autumn, therefore lowering the score of negative self-assessment by using a process guide is not proved. But running process guide in more semesters could change the picture. The "moments of programming" self-assessments tool is useful for evaluating how the students are confident with the general programming, IDE and compiler progress during the semester. Further work must be carried out in the coming semesters to really observe the effect of the process guideline.

REFERENCES

- [1] Gorson, J., O'Rourke, E. (2020, August). Why do CS1 Students Think They are Bad at Programming? Proceedings of the 2020 ACM Conference on International Computing Education Research. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1145/3372782.3406273>
- [2] Kinnunen, P., Simon, B. (2011, August 8). CS majors' self-efficacy perceptions in CS1. Proceedings of the Seventh International Workshop on Computing Education Research. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1145/2016911.2016917>
- [3] Kinnunen, P., Simon, B. (2012). My program is ok – am I? Computing freshmen's experiences of doing programming assignments. Computer Science Education, 22(1), 1–28. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08993408.2012.655091>
- [4] Albert Bandura (1977) Self-efficacy: Toward a Unifying Theory of Behavioral Change, Stanford University, Psychological Review 1977, Vol. 84, No. 2, 191-215
- [5] Steinhorst, P., Petersen, A., Vahrenhold, J. (2020, August). Revisiting self-efficacy in introductory programming. Proceedings of the 2020 ACM Conference on International Computing Education Research. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1145/3372782.3406281>
- [6] Prather, J., Pettit, R., McMurry, K., Peters, A., Homer, J., & Cohen, M. (2018, August 8). Metacognitive difficulties faced by novice programmers in automated assessment tools. Proceedings of the 2018 ACM Conference on International Computing Education Research. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1145/3230977.3230981>
- [7] Loksa, D., Ko, A. J., Jernigan, W., Oleson, A., Mendez, C. J., & Burnett, M. M. (2016, May 7). Programming, problem solving, and self-awareness. Proceedings of the 2016 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1145/2858036.2858252>
- [8] O. Schultz, T. Students' metacognitive processes and impact on Self-efficacy in embedded programming <https://orbit.dtu.dk/en/publications/students-metacognitive-processes-and-impact-on-self-efficacy-in-e>
- [9] The self-assessment survey used 13 moments of programming included vignettes <https://sites.google.com/site/smartiot4s/didatics/moments-of-programming-vignettes>
- [10] Results for all 13 moments of programming <https://sites.google.com/site/smartiot4s/didatics/moments-of-programming-vignettes/negative-self-assessment-in-of-total-participant>